

Advancement in bioremediation process: A mini review

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ABSTRACT

Bioremediation has recently evolved as an emerging green technology of environmental conservation by removing, transforming and breaking down various contaminants especially petroleum hydrocarbons applying living organisms. Different technologies for carrying out bioremediation have been considered in this paper. In this respect, biotechnological approaches especially biostimulation and bioaugmentation have gained a great deal of attention in recent years. Recent studies have shown that a combination of both approaches is equally feasible but does not explicitly more efficiently or beneficially. Exploring of suitable technology on contaminant sites need specific requirements such as availability of microorganisms with degrading capability in sufficient quantities, nutrient availability to support microbial growth and proliferation as well as suitable environmental parameters such as pH, temperature, O₂ etc. in combination with duration of exposure. Such technologies could be of help towards eventual manipulation for making bioremediation easy to apply technically and economically viable for comprehensive pollutants treatments.

1. Introduction

Bioremediation is defined as the process by which microorganisms are stimulated to rapidly degrade hazardous organic pollutants to environmentally safe levels in soils, sediments, substances, materials and ground water. Recently, biological remediation process has also been devised to either precipitate effectively immobilize inorganic pollutants such as heavy metals. Stimulation of microorganisms is achieved by the addition of growth substances, nutrients, terminal electron acceptor/donors or some combination thereby resulting in an increase in organic pollutant degradation and bio-transformation. The energy and carbon are obtained through the metabolism of organic compounds by the microbes involved in bioremediation processes (Fulekar et al. 2009).

Bioremediation process goes through transforming contaminants to non-hazardous or less hazardous chemicals. Often, the micro-organisms metabolize the chemicals to

produce carbon dioxide or methane, water and biomass. Biotransformation is any alteration of the molecule or structure of a compound by micro-organisms. Furthermore, biodegradation is the breaking down of organic or bioaccumulation and biotransformation of inorganic compounds into environmental friendly compounds.

Microorganisms individually cannot mineralize all hazardous compounds. Consortium of microorganisms leads to complete mineralization through a sequential degradation by synergism and co metabolism actions. Natural communities of microorganisms in various environments have a tremendous physiological versatility, they are able to metabolize and often mineralize an enormous variety of organic substances. Certain communities of bacteria and fungi metabolize some multitude molecules that can be as a result of microbial activity in one environment or another. Most bioremediation systems mostly carried out under aerobic conditions, but running a system under anaerobic conditions (Colberg and Young 1995) may allow microbial

Fig. 1 Proposed Mechanisms of bioremediation (Malik 2006)

organisms to degrade otherwise recalcitrant molecules (Fig. 1). Based upon the process of removal and transportation of wastes, bioremediation technology can be carried out *in situ* and *ex situ*. *In situ* bioremediation deals with pollutants treatments at the same site, while *ex situ* involves the removal of contaminated material completely from one site and its transfer to another site.

When both methods have been compared, it was found that the rate of consistency and biodegradation of process outcomes differ between *ex situ* and *in situ* methods. *Ex situ*

bioremediation costs is high when compared to *in situ*, where there is need for excavation of contaminated samples to be treated. *In situ* and *ex situ* bioremediation methods depends essentially on microbial metabolism, however, *in situ* methods are preferred over *ex situ* for ecological restoration of contaminated soil, water and environment (Vidali 2001). The current paper focuses on various technologies of microbial bioremediation. The gathered information is valuable to design reactors for contaminants elimination.

Fig. 2 *In situ* bioremediation technologies

2. Some bioremediation processes

2.1. Field bioremediation technologies (*In situ*)

In situ bioremediation applies to treat contaminated groundwater and soil at site with minimal disturbance as shown in figure 2 and table 1.

2.1.1. Bioventing

Bioventing is the one vital tool *in situ* treatment technique. This technology is designed primarily to treat soil contamination by fuels, nonhalogenated volatile organic compounds (VOCs), herbicides, semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs), and pesticides. The technology need for the presence of indigenous organisms capable of

degrading the contaminants, as well as nutrients essential for their growth. This process is an aerobic that involving air supply for the biodegradation and minimizing volatilization in order to release of contaminants into the atmosphere.

2.1.2. Biostimulation

It is one of the *in situ* bioremediation techniques for treatments of subsurface region by supplying the water-based solutions which carrying nutrients, electron acceptor, or other amendments. This technology is applied primarily to treat soil and groundwater contaminated with fuels, nonhalogenated VOCs, SVOCs, pesticides, and herbicides. It requires the presence of indigenous organisms capable of degrading the contaminants under investigation.

Table 1 Methods applied in bioremediation process (Vidali 2001; Shukla et al. 2010)

Technique	Examples	Benefits	Applications
<i>In situ</i>	Biosparging	Most efficient Non Invasive	Biodegradative abilities of indigenous microorganisms Presence of metals and inorganic compounds
	Bioventing	Relative passive	Environmental parameters Biodegradability of ollutants
	Bioaugmentation	Naturally attenuated process, treat soil and water	Chemical solubility Geological factors Distribution of pollutants
<i>Ex situ</i>	Land farming (Solid-phase treatment system)	Cost efficient ,Simple, Inexpensive ,self-heating	Surface application, aerobic process, application of organic materials to natural soils followed by irrigation and tilling
	Composting (Anaerobic, converts solid organic wastes into humus-like material)	Low cost Rapid reaction rate, Inexpensive, self heating	To make plants healthier good alternative to land filling or incinerating practical and convenient.
	Biopiles	Can be done on site	Surface application, agricultural to municipal waste
Bioreactors	Slurry reactors	Rapid degradation kinetic Optimized environmental parameters	Bioaugmentat Toxicity of amendments
	Aqueous reactors	Enhances mass transfer Effective use of inoculants and surfactant	Toxic concentrations of contaminants
Precipitation or Flocculation	Non-directed physico-chemical complexation reaction between dissolved contaminants and charged cellular components (dead Biomass)	Cost-effective	Removal of heavy Metals
Microfiltration	Microfiltration membranes are used at a constant pressure	Remove dissolved solids rapidly	Waste water treatment; recovery and reuse of more than 90% of original waste water
Electrodialysis	Uses cation and anion exchange membrane pairs	Withstand high temperature and can be reused	Removal of dissolved solids efficiently

2.1.3. Air Sparging

Air sparging is usually fortified to contaminated ground water by injecting air below the water table, so it is *in situ* treatment. Air sparging is designed primarily to treat groundwater contamination with fuels, nonhalogenated VOCs, organics, SVOCs, pesticides, and herbicides. This technology requires the presence of indigenous organisms capable of degrading the contaminants of interest, as well as nutrients necessary for growth and specific contaminant availability.

2.1.4. Natural Attenuation

It focuses on the verification and monitoring of passive natural remediation processes (Khan et al. 2004), *in situ* bioremediation, bioattenuation, and intrinsic remediation. Natural attenuation is an *in situ* treatment method that uses natural processes to limit the spread of contamination and to reduce the concentration and the amount of pollutants at contaminated stations (Boparai et al. 2008; Khan et al. 2004). This indicates that the environmental contaminants are undisturbed during natural attenuation. Natural attenuation processes are often categorized as destructive or nondestructive (Gelman and Binstock 2008). These contaminants include fuels, nonhalogenated VOCs, SVOCs, pesticides, and herbicides. The process could deal with halogenated organics, but it requires longer treatment times. Also, the technology is manipulated to treat especially hydrophobic contaminants such as high molecular weight petrochemicals that tend to absorb strongly to soil particles and have very low rates of imbibition. Often, communities of adapted degraders will mineralize these contaminants quickly after its absorption to soil particles.

2.1.5. Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation is using of plants for the treatment/mineralization of pollutants. Pollutants can be taken up inside plant tissues (phytoextraction), rhizofiltration, transformed by different plant enzymes (phytotransformation), volatilize through plants into the atmosphere (phytovolatilization), degraded by different microorganisms in the root zone (rhizoremediation) or added to soil material (phytostabilization) (Salt et al. 1998; Pilon-Smits 2005).

Phytoremediation may be used for degrading soil and groundwater contaminated with toxic heavy metals, organic (chlorinated solvents), radionuclides, contaminants, BTEX compounds, nonaromatic petroleum hydrocarbons, nitrotoluene ammunition wastes, and excess nutrients (Schnoor et al. 1995).

2.1.6. Bioaugmentation

It is the introduction of a group of natural microbial strains or genetically engineered strains to treat contaminated soil or water. It involves group of microbes like nematodes, bacteria, protozoa, rotifers, and fungi capable of degrading organic compounds.

2.2. Field bioremediation (*Ex situ*)

It is applying to soil and groundwater (Fig. 3) at the site which has been removed via excavation (soil) or pumping (water). Bisht et al. (2014) have utilized of endophytic strain *Bacillus* sp. SBER3 for biodegradation of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) in soil model system.

Fig. 3 *Ex situ* bioremediation technologies

2.2.1. Composting

Composting technology is combining contaminated soil with nonhazardous organic matter such as manure or biological wastes which supports the growth of microbes.

2.2.2. Land farming

Land farming technology involves the application of polluted material that has been excavated onto the soil surface and regularly tilled to mix with aeration (Harmsen et al. 2007; Maciel et al. 2009). In cases of very shallow contamination, the top layer of site may be tilled without requiring any excavation. Leachate could be controlled with Liners or other methods. This method is designed primarily to treat soil contamination by fuels, nonhalogenated VOCs, SVOCs, pesticides, and herbicides. The process may be applied to degrade halogenated organics but it is less effective. Although the technology is very simple and cheap, it requires large amount of space, and reduction in contaminant concentrations which sometimes might be due to volatilization rather than biodegradation (Souza et al. 2009; Sanscartier et al. 2010).

2.2.3. Solid Phase Treatment under Controlled conditions

It includes preparation of treatment matrix beds which containing bio-treatment cells and soil piles or composting. Heat, Moisture, nutrients, oxygen, and pH can be adjusted to enhance biodegradation. These technologies differ from land farming where the treatment processes are often enclosed to control off-gases. Typically, excavated material is mixed with amendments of soil and placed on area for treatment that includes leachate collection systems with some of aeration. These technologies require a lot of space and excavation of contaminated material. One advantage for *ex situ* methods is that toxic byproducts or metabolites formed during the biodegradation process is contained within it.

2.2.4. Biological Treatment with Slurry-Phase

This technology involves the treatment of excavated soil in the environment under control within bioreactors. Excavated soil is processed to separate stones and rubble, and then mixed with water to certain concentration depending upon the concentration of contaminants, rate of biodegradation, and physical nature of the soils. Electron acceptors and nutrients are added to the reactor, and parameters such as pH and temperature are controlled to enhance the biological processes. Also, the reactor may be inoculated with specific micro-organisms if a suitable population is not suitable or present. Targeted contaminants include pesticides, petrochemicals, solvents and preservatives of wood, explosives, petroleum hydrocarbons, and other organic chemicals.

Bioreactors are favored over *in situ* biological technologies for heterogeneous soils, due to low soils permeability, areas where underlying groundwater would be difficult to hold, or when rapid treatments are required. Similar to solid phase *ex situ* treatments have the advantage of containing toxic metabolites such as vinyl chloride. Slurry-phase treatment tends to be rapid, but more expensive, than controlled solid phase treatment.

There many factors affecting bioremediation such as: bioactivity, energy sources, bioavailability, biochemistry, pH, temperature, toxicity of compounds, Water contents and geological characteristics, external electron availability, and nutrient availability. Advantages for bioremediation are effective, economical, ecofriendly, less toxic by-products generation, on-site treatment possible and have no effect on natural flora. However, there are many difficult to apply bioremediation that are it need specific environmental condition required, specific microflora required, and long time required to remove or transform contaminant.

3. Advancement in bioremediation field

Advances in biotechnological tools and techniques, and their application in biological system helped in overcoming various limitations associated with traditional bioremediation processes in order to enhance these processes. It has been found that the following steps were enhanced or play an important role in bioremediation process:

3.1. Application of biosurfactants in bioremediation

Hydrophobic pollutants bioavailability of targeted compounds was one of the main problems in bioremediation. This was mainly attributed to the hydrophobic nature of contaminants. The application of most chemical surfactants helps to overcome these problems associated with hydrophobic contaminants. Searching for green and cost-effective technology, was found that many biological molecules are amphiphilic and partitions favorable at interphases (Banat et al. 2000). Microbial compounds, which exhibit particularly high surface and emulsifying activity, are known as biosurfactants (Banat et al. 2000).

Biosurfactants are surface-active substances synthesized by living cells. Attention with microbial surfactants has been steadily increasing in recent years due to their diversity, friendly nature with environment, possibility of large-scale production, selectivity, performance under extreme conditions, and its protection potential applications in environments (Banat et al. 2000; Rahman et al. 2002). Biosurfactants are diverse, available and highly diverse because of many different genes of microbes producing them (Ron and Rosenberg 2002; Bodour et al. 2004). Therefore, the use of biosurfactants will reduce the hydrophobicity of compounds and make it readily available to different biological systems for their remediation.

3.2. Role of oxygen releasing compounds in promoting aerobic bioremediation process

Oxygen is typically the rate determining factor in aerobic bioremediation at different environments. The degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons occurs much faster with the presence of oxygen compared to its absence. So, the addition of oxygen can significantly increase the process of remediation rate. Application of oxygen releasing compound (ORC) is one way to increase the rate of bioremediation process. It has been determined that ORC releases oxygen slowly when it comes in contact with water. It can be applied

using retrievable filter socks placed in monitoring wells or as a slurry mixture.

3.3. Microbes assisted phytoremediation

Phytoremediation together with microbes tackles the targeted contaminant compounds and enhances the remediation process. Many researchers in this area have carried out extensive works which have potential field applications. There are many innovative techniques in the field of bioremediation which have drawn attention of researchers such as nanobiotechnology; genetic engineering; culture of recombinant microorganisms; cells of animals and plants; metabolic engineering; hybridoma technology; bioelectronics; protein engineering; transgenic animals and plants; organ and tissue engineering; immunological assays; genomics and proteomics; and bioseparations and bioreactor technologies (Gavrilescu and Chisti 2005; Kulshreshtha 2012). Bisht et al. (2015) have studied the bioremediation of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) using rhizosphere technology and declared the importance of the synergistic use of plant and associated microbial communities for bioremediation resulting in rhizoremediation, could solve some of the problems encountered during the application of both individual techniques *i.e.* bioaugmentation and phytoremediation.

We anticipate that these techniques reflect promising perspective towards the remediation, but at the same time need lots of work to implement these modern and fascinating technologies at the field level. There are a lot of genetic engineering techniques applications which might be used in the bioremediation process like genetically modified organisms (microbes), but their field applications are strictly regulated due to several environmental risks associated with these organisms. Some studies gave a promising result with the application of transgenic plants and transgenic microbes in phytoremediation field (Pieper and Reineke 2000; Eapen et al. 2007).

4. Role of biomolecular tools and techniques in bioremediation

Majority of the microbes are uncultivable in laboratory conditions, but their role in the particular niche cannot be neglected particularly in the process like bioremediation. In order to trace the microbial population and their role in the environment, molecular techniques proved to be a boon in this field. The genes involved in the bioremediation of the polluted compounds and their respective enzymes can be traced and hence in turn the microbial flora involved in the bioremediation process could be traced. It also helps to record the metabolic pathway followed by the organism in order to degrade particular contaminated compounds.

5. Bioinformatics in bioremediation

Pre-information of cellular processes associated with bioremediation bioinformatics tools have been tried to identify and analyze various components of cells such as gene and protein functions, interactions, and metabolic and regulatory pathways. Bioinformatics analysis will facilitate

and quicken the understanding of different cellular process, and cellular mechanism in order to control microbial cells which act as factories. The next decade will belong to understanding molecular mechanism and cellular manipulation using the integration of bioinformatics. Bioinformatics has a wide application in bioremediation especially in the structure–function relationship and pathways of biodegradation of xenobiotics (Fulekar and Sharma, 2008).

6. Role of nanotechnology in bioremediation process

Nanotechnology is an emerging branch of science which has attracted the interest of researchers involved in varied subject due to its size and effective results. It involves varied applications including designing, characterization, production, and application of particles by controlling their size to nanoscale. Nanoworld seems to be fascinating and highly promising approach to get a clean environment free from contaminated pollutants. Recently, several scientists evaluated the significant role of nanotechnology in the field of remediation (Bhakta et al., 2016). There are many more advances in field of bioremediation which helps to overcome various hurdles in bioremediation process during treating of complex contaminants. With the introduction of new tools and technologies every day in this field of study, new insight to research is added.

7. Applications of bioremediation

Till now we have discussed the fundamentals on which the technology of bioremediation stands. It is very essential to realize and understand these principles before we think of the practical implementation where the main bioremediation objectives stages were covered. The process of bioremediation fundamentals translating into field applications is not an easy task. It requires a judicious exchange of skills among professionals from various disciplines.

Bioremediation can be performed *in-situ* or off-site. The decision often depends upon the nature of contaminant, objective of the remedial action, availability of funds/time and viewpoints of the local people and authorities. Whenever the pollution effects shallow soil layers, excavation and subsequent treatment at other sites (off-site bioremediation) is recommended either in a biopile (contaminant material is piled on the ground surface) or biocell (contaminant material is deposited and treated underground at a clean site) both of which must be lined to confine the contaminant and leachates.

7.1. Microbes in reclamation of wastelands including oil spills

Petroleum hydrocarbons, although not xenobiotics, are one of the main potential sources of environmental contamination due to their large-scale use. Soil and groundwater are often contaminated with gasoline or diesel fuel from leaking underground storage tanks and because of accidental spills and leakage from pipelines. These

compounds may cause considerable damage not only in soils but also in water intakes or groundwater reservoirs. As a consequence, cost-effective bioremediation techniques have been developed during this period, especially to clean up oil- and gas-polluted sites. Petroleum contaminated soils and aquifers constitute about 60% of the sites where bioremediation is being used in field demonstrations or full-scale operations (Malik, 2006).

7.1.1. Microbial remediation of oil contaminated site

The basic steps involved in the development of such bioremediation strategies are (i) Microbe isolation and identification, (ii) Selection of petroleum degrading bacteria, (iii) Generation of biomass, (iv) Application of biomass to the contaminated site and (v) Maintenance of the selected bacterial population at the site

(i) Microbe isolation and identification - Microbe is usually isolated by inoculating trypticase soya broth with the contaminated soil. To enrich the petroleum degrading bacteria a two layered medium comprising lower layer of minimal nitrogen medium (nitrogen source) covered with petroleum layer (carbon source) can be used. After 48 hours of

incubation, the petroleum degrading bacteria can be streaked on trypticase soy agar plate and incubated for 2-3 days. The developed colonies are picked and again inoculated on two layered medium till the pure bacterial cultures are obtained. The bacterial identification can be done by standard biochemical tests, fatty acid analysis or by 16 S rDNA analysis. Care should be taken that the selected organisms are non-pathogenic. It is better to conduct the screening and isolation at around 20°C temperatures as most of the pathogens best survive around 37°C. However, further confirmation must be done to ensure the non-pathogenic nature before proceeding with the bioremediation experiments. Steps in bioremediation of petroleum contaminated site are shown in the following figure (Malik, 2006).

(ii) Selection of petroleum degrading bacteria - Confirmation of the petroleum biodegradation ability of the selected strains should be done by inoculating petroleum laden sterile soil with the selected culture and incubating it for about 15 days. Total bacterial count and total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) of the samples can be monitored to select the most efficient strains.

Fig. 4 Steps of bioremediation for treating petroleum contaminated site

(iii) Generation of biomass - After the microorganism has been identified and its ability to degrade petroleum oil has been tested in the laboratory, the next step is to increase the number of microorganisms for field application. Biomass production is done in large fermentors and the subsequent culture is concentrated (by high speed centrifugation) to produce mud like precipitated cells. The concentrated biomass is packed in plastic, tight sealing bags and transported to the contaminated site on ice.

(iv) Application of biomass to the contaminated site - Biomass should be applied to the contaminated soil as soon as possible but before 48 hours of production. The amount of biomass to be applied depends on the total area of the contaminated site as well as the degree of contamination. The biomass is appropriately diluted and applied to the contaminated soil by injection or spray technique. If the contamination is in the upper layers (2-3 feet of surface soil), spraying of the diluted biomass after agitation of the soil may suffice but if the contamination has reached lower layers, injection of the biomass to the deeper soil layers is required. Since the ultraviolet rays from sun are lethal to the microorganisms, the application of biomass to soil should be best made in the early morning hours before sunrise.

(v) Maintenance of the selected bacterial population at the site - Since the soil has been augmented with more than natural microbial load of that particular soil, special attention needs to be paid to monitor and maintain the oxygen levels, nutrients, water content and pH so that the selected population can effectively degrade the contaminants.

7.1.2. Petroleum degradation with microorganisms

Several petroleum degrading microbes have been identified till date as listed by many researchers. These groups were identified as actinomycetes, coryneforms, Enterobacteriaceae, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Micrococcus* spp. (two clusters), *Nocardia* species (two clusters), *Pseudomonas* spp. (two clusters), and *Sphaerotilus natans* which indicated that degradation of petroleum is accomplished by a diverse range of bacterial taxa. A survey of petroleum-degrading bacteria was carried out in several parts around the world to evaluate the distribution of the naturally occurring petroleum-degrading aerobic bacteria. Depending on the location, 0.08–2.0% of the heterotrophic could degrade crude petroleum hydrocarbons as the sole source of carbon. *Nocardia*, *Pseudomonas*, *Mycobacterium*, *Klebsiella*, *Acinetobacter* and *Micrococcus* were the most common petroleum degraders. Selected strains belonging to *Pseudomonas*, *Mycobacterium*, and *Nocardia* (one strain) degraded 47–78% of Arab-Mix crude oil over a period of 20 days.

The Energy Research Institute (TERI), India has developed the Oilzapper which is crude oil and oily sludge degrading bacterial consortium. This microbial consortium, developed from five bacterial isolates (obtained from hydrocarbon-contaminated sites), was immobilized with a suitable carrier material (powdered corncob). The immobilized culture (oilzapper), which has the survivability of three months at ambient temperature, can be sealed aseptically into sterile polythene bags and transported to the contaminated site. It has been successfully used for cleanup

of crude oil spills and treatment of oily sludge. More than 40,000 tonnes of oily sludge/oil contaminated soil and drill cuttings have been treated at various locations. More than 30,000 tonnes of oily sludge/oil contaminated soil is under treatment at different locations in India and the Middle East countries.

Further research targets more effective translation of lab results into the real field situations. Poor performance of *in situ* treatments involving the addition of bacteria have been result to the unknown effects of site conditions on the ability of bacteria to degrade contaminants. Specialized indicator strains of bacteria that produce light in response to the presence of bioavailable polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) are being developed. The indicator strains would enable us to predetermine, whether or not the appropriate nutrient and environmental conditions exist at a site. Microencapsulated bacteria for low-cost bioremediation of petroleum products that are less degraded by naturally-occurring bacteria are also being examined (Malik 2006).

A recent case study demonstrated bioremediation of soil contaminated with diesel in laboratory conditions as well as the *in-situ* bioremediation of a natural diesel spill (400,000 l). Diesel fuel is a complex mixture of alkanes, and aromatic compounds obtained from the middle-distillate, gas-oil fraction during petroleum separation. In this paper the different approaches of bioremediation were tested under laboratory conditions. The experimental set comprised of control experiment (Heat-sterilised soil), natural attenuation (No amendment), biostimulation (with a. inorganic N and P source, b. Sterilized sewage sludge), bioaugmentation (live/active sewage sludge). The authors found best diesel biodegradation when biostimulation with inorganic nutrients was done. In both laboratory and field scale studies, the hydrocarbon degraders (*Acinetobacter* & *Pseudomonas* species) were found abundant. Therefore, based on the lab results, for the real oil spills an integrated approach of physical removal of diesel (free product recovery) followed by tilling and fertilizing biostimulation treatment was recommended. Oil contaminated soil in Kuwait could be successfully bioremediated by land-farming within 12 months. Land-farming could be enhanced by adjusting the C: N ratio to 50:1, inoculating soil with HUB (hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria), and adding vegetation (alfa-alfa inoculated with rhizobium cultures) after partial TPH (total petroleum hydrocarbon) reduction. Such enhanced land-farming resulted in degradation of 90% of TPH from light contaminated soil. McBean (1995) suggested an *ex-situ* two-stage process for remediation of semi-volatile organic compounds. The first stage comprised of excavation, heap piling and washing of contaminated soil in presence of surfactants, while in the second stage the collected leachate was biologically treated with removal efficiency of 90% or more. Such a process with decoupled stages has dual advantage that is quick leaching and soil replacement as well as differential optimization of each step.

7.1.3. Hydrocarbon degradation with biosurfactants

Biosurfactants are surfactants which are biologically produced by yeast or bacteria from various substrates including sugars, oils, alkanes and wastes. Examples include rhamnolipids (produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*),

sophorolipids (produced by *Candida bombicola*) and surfactin (produced by *Bacillus subtilis*). Biosurfactants have shown their potential for remediation of contaminated soil and water. Chemical compounds contaminants can be treated through desorption or biodegradation processes.

Addition of *Pseudomonas* sp. DS10-129 rhamnolipid along with poultry litter and coir pith has been found to enhance *ex situ* bioremediation of soil contaminated with gasoline. Rhamnolipids from *P. aeruginosa* UG2 were also able to effectively eliminate a hydrocarbon mixture from a sandy loam soil and that the degree of removal (from 23 to 59%) was dependent on the hydrocarbon type removed and the concentration of the surfactant used. Surfactant produced by a strain of *Bacillus subtilis* could eliminate 62% of the oil in a sand pack saturated with kerosene and thus could be used for *in situ* removing of oil and cleaning sludge from sludge tanks. The use of the biosurfactants in cleaning oil from coastal sand, and from the feathers and furs of marine birds and animals has also been evaluated. The biosurfactant (PS-17) produced by strain *Pseudomonas* PS-17 could efficiently remove oil from sand (95% removal) as well as from feathers (85%) and furs (82%) of marine birds and animals contaminated by oil as opposed to 1-2% oil removal in the absence of PS-17 biosurfactant. The biosurfactants seem to enhance biodegradation by influencing the bioavailability of the contaminant. They are very promising for use in remediation technologies because of their biodegradability and low toxicity (Malik 2006). Additionally, It has been concluded that the selection of rhizobacteria, which are able to produce biosurfactants in the rhizosphere of the plants, is an interesting alternative to improve the pollutants removal efficiency (Plociniczak et al. 2011).

8. Mechanism of biodegradation

Microbes play an important role in bioremediation as they generate the enzymes that catalyze the degradative reactions. Microbes possess the essential enzyme system which could use organic substances as a source of carbon and energy. Therefore, microbes gain energy and raw material essential for their multiplication and maintenance from organic wastes degradation. However, several xenobiotic contaminants might be eliminated through a group of diverse microorganism with a wide different types of enzyme systems.

8.1. Reductive dehalogenation

This mechanism plays very important role in the detoxification of halogenated organic contaminants, where microorganism replace halogen atom of contaminant with hydrogen atom. Thus the reaction adds 2 electrons to contaminant and reduces it. It has been found that the dehalogenated derivatives are less toxic and easily go through further microbial decay.

8.2. Cometabolism

It leads to no benefit to the cell. This non-beneficial transformation is often termed as secondary utilization, cometabolism or gratuitous metabolism. One form of secondary substrate transformation is co-metabolism in which

enzymes produced for oxidation of primary substrate are capable of degrading the secondary substrate fortuitously. It is thus defined as degradation of a compound only in presence of other simple organic compound that utilized as a primary energy source. Several contaminants such as Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and pesticides are degraded through cometabolism mechanism. An emerging application is the introducing of water containing dissolved primary substrate through injection (e.g. methane, toluene) and oxygen into ground water to support the cometabolic breakdown of targeted organic contaminants. The addition of methane or methanol supports methanotrophic activity, which has been demonstrated powerful to degrade chlorinated solvents, such as vinyl chloride and Trichloroethane (TCE), by co-metabolism.

8.3. Contaminant structure vs biodegradability relation

Biodegradability is essential for bioremediation of organic pollutants. Pollutant Chemical structure governs the ability of microorganisms to metabolize them, specifically with the time and the degree of degradation. As it has been discussed above, some compounds are readily biodegradable whereas others are not. Let us look at the general rules that determine this. Low to mid molecular weight hydrocarbons and alcohols represent readily biodegradable chemicals. The straight-chain and simple non-aromatic compounds are easily degraded than branched and polynuclear compounds.

Halocarbons are resistant to biodegradation (xenobiotic compounds) and are often termed as Dioxins are very difficult to degrade. The rate of biodegradation is increased with increasing degree of halogenation. For example, Dichloromethane as well as Monochloro biphenyls are degraded fast as these are used as growth requirements. On the other hand, Trichloroethane or TCE (widely used solvent) and Polychlorinated biphenyls are not used as carbon/energy source and are degraded with cometabolic route slowly.

8.4. Bioremediation Microorganisms/Agents

Different microorganisms are able to degrade wide range of contaminants depending upon the nature and concentration of contaminant and the growth requirements of the microorganisms. Researchers all over the world are continuously working to find out novel and more potent biodegraders. The following points are an important in microbial bioremediation microorganisms' process:

Pure cultures - One should have pure cultures to work on in order to be able to evaluate the efficiency of microbes in such systems, most of the laboratory studies focus on biodegradative capacity of pure cultures. *Pseudomonas* species are most widely detected microbes in the contaminated site due to their extensive biodegradation abilities. One of the most important fungal organisms is phanerochaete which proposed for the biodegradation of various pollutants such as high molecular weight polynuclear aromatics like benzo (a) pyrene, DDT, TNT, and plastics such as polyethylene.

Adaptive microorganisms and molecular breeding - Naturally occurring microbiota may not be capable of degrading certain compounds or certain categories of compounds at different metabolic ranges. There it may be necessary to supplement with the specialized microbes. Such microorganism is developing by repeatedly exposing them to higher concentration of contaminants. Often the microorganisms with specialized degradation ability can also be enriched from the contaminated site. To achieve a complete catabolic pathway for a xenobiotic compound is the ultimate objective for its biodegradative capacity. Microbes metabolic pathways are under constant evolution and this process can be accelerated by plasmid mediated genetic exchange, recombination. A specially constructed *Pseudomonas* strain in this way has been found to be potent for degradation of chlorophenols and chlorobenzoate.

Crucial points in pollution control - In basic, the pollutants are permitting to become physically spread out, thereby reducing their concentration. They are dispersal and consequently diluted to a given substance concentration depends on its nature and the characteristics of the specific pathway used to achieve this. It may take place, with varying degrees of effectiveness, in air, water or soil. Air movement gives good dispersal and dilution of gaseous emissions. However, heavier particulates tend to fall out near the source. Water give a good dispersal and dilution potential in large bodies of water or rivers. On the other hand, smaller watercourses clearly lead to lower capacity. It is also obvious that moving bodies of water disperse pollutants more rapidly than still ones. Movement through the soil represents another opportunity for dilution and dispersion approach, often with soil water is playing a significant part, and typically aided by the activities of resident living organisms.

Contaminants concentration - The previous term is relying on the pollutant becoming attenuated and spread over a wide area, however contaminants concentration is an attempt to gather together the offending substance and prevent its distribution into the surrounding environment. This contradiction between these two general methods is an enduring feature of environmental biotechnology and, though the fashion changes from time to time, favoring first one and then the other. The specific modalities of the particular methods are often more important concerns than the more theoretically applicable general considerations.

Practical toxicity issues - How the toxic action of pollutants arises? Usually pollutants arise 'directly' and 'indirectly'. In the first method, the effect arises by the contaminant combining with organisms' cellular constituents or enzymes and thus preventing their proper function. In the latter, the damage is done by secondary action resulting from their presence, typified by histamine reactions in allergic responses.

The significance of natural cycles to the practical applications of environmental biotechnology is a point that has already been considered. In different aspects the functional toxicity of a pollution event is often no more than the obverse aspect of this same coin, in that it is frequently an overburdening of existing innate systems which constitutes the problem. Thus the difficulty lies in an inability to deal

with the contaminant by normal pathways, rather than the simple presence of the substance itself. The case of metals is a good example. Under normal environmental conditions, processes of weathering, erosion and volcanic activity lead to their continuous release into the environment and corresponding natural mechanisms exist to remove them from circulation, at a broadly equivalent rate. However, human activities, particularly after the advent of industrialization, have seriously disrupted these cycles in respect of certain metals, perhaps most notably cadmium, lead, mercury and silver. While the human contribution is, clearly, taken into consider, it is also important to be aware that there are additional potential aspects of pollution and that other metals, even though natural fluxes remain their dominant global source, may also give rise to severe localized contamination at times.

The toxicity of metals is related to their place in the periodic table and reflects their affinity for amino and sulphhydryl groups (associated with active sites on enzymes). In broad terms, Type-A metals are less toxic than type-B, but this is only a generalization and a number of other factors exert an influence in real-life situations. Passive uptake by plants is a two-stage process, beginning with an initial binding onto the cell wall followed by diffusion into the inside the cell, along a concentration gradient. Thus, those cations which readily associate with particulates are accumulated more easily than those which do not. In addition, the presence of chelating ligands may affect the bio-availability and thus, the resultant toxicity of metals. Whereas some metal-organic complexes (Cu-EDTA for example) can detoxify certain metals, lipophilic organometallic complexes can increase uptake and thereby the functional toxic effect observed. Although it has been considering the issue of metal toxicity in relation to the contamination of land or water, it also has relevance elsewhere and may be of particular importance in other applications of biotechnologies to environmental problems. For example, anaerobic digestion is an engineered microbial process commonly employed in the water industry for sewage treatment and gaining high acceptance for biowaste management. The effects of metal cations within anaerobic bioreactors have indicated that the pollutants concentration is the key factor. However, the situation is not entirely clear cut as the interactions between cations under anaerobic conditions may lead to increased or decreased effective toxicity in line with the series of synergistic/antagonistic relationships. Toxicity is often dependent on the form in which the substance occurs and substances forming analogues which closely mimic the properties of essential chemicals are typically readily taken up and/or accumulated.

9. Practical applications to pollution control

Bacteria are the main inhabiting microorganism to an aqueous environment which clearly presents a problem for air remediation. Usually, the resolution is to dissolve the contaminant in water, which is then subjected to bioremediation by bacteria, as in the following descriptions. The scope for future development of a complementary solution is utilizing the fact that many species of yeast

produce aerial hyphae which may be able to metabolize material directly from the air through the following trends.

Biofilters - Microorganisms degrade components of the resultant contaminants solution, thereby bringing about the desired effect. The medium itself provides physical support for microbial growth, with a large surface area to volume ratio, high in internal void spaces and rich in nutrients to stimulate and sustain bacterial activity. Biofilters need to be watered sufficiently to maintain optimum internal conditions, but waterlogging is to be avoided as this leads to compaction, and hence, reduced efficiency. Properly maintained, biofilters can reduce odor release by 95% or more.

Biotrickling filters - It can deal with higher concentrations of contaminant and has a significantly smaller foot-print than a biofilter of the same throughput capacity.

Bioscrubbers - Bioscrubber is not a biological treatment system, but rather a highly efficient method of removing odour components by dissolving them. Unsurprisingly, then, it is most appropriate for hydrophilic compounds like acetone or methanol.

The gas to be treated passes through a fine water spray generated as a mist or curtain within the body of the bioscrubber vessel. The contaminant is absorbed into the water, which subsequently collect to form a reservoir at the bottom. The contaminant solution is then removed to a secondary bioreactor where the actual process of biodegradation takes place. In practice, activated sludge systems are often used in this role. As in the preceding case, process control can be achieved by monitoring the water phase and adding nutrients, buffers or fresh water as appropriate.

10. Pollutants uptake problems

The pollution of many water coastal and inland all over the world is a well-documented environmental problem and wider use of these nontoxic, readily biodegradable alternatives products which could make a huge difference. Cost is a major concern, as biolubricants are around twice as expensive as their conventional equivalents, while for some more specialist formulations the difference is significantly greater. Though, inevitably, users need to be convinced of the deliverable commercial benefits, the potential market is enormous. The petrochemical industry has thought to meet the growing demand for more environmentally friendly products by developing biodegradable lubricants based on crude oil.

11. Conclusion

Bioremediation is the dealing with the environmental pollution that is in fact a natural process. Different approaches to accelerate the intrinsic bioremediation have been developed and used at a number of sites worldwide. In most cases, single technology fails to work in field due to various environmental factors associated and the toxicity of targeted compounds. Hence, there is a need to develop consecutive technologies which can fit to ever-changing

environmental conditions and toxicity of the compound. There is an urgent demand of scientific and engineering inputs to be incorporated to these technologies for field applications to make clean environment.

Nowadays, techniques are improving and produce a greater knowledge and experience, where bioremediation has gained triumph for dealing with certain types of site contamination. Unfortunately, the principles, techniques, advantages, and disadvantages of bioremediation are not well known or understood. Recombinant DNA technology is the future hope to improve or increase the ability of pollutant-degrading microbes through strain improvement and genetic modification of specific regulatory and metabolic genes that are important in developing safe, effective, and economical techniques for bioremediation.

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